

The Role of Organizational Well-Being in Companies: A Conceptual Literature Review

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Abstract

Organizational well-being encompasses a set of factors that influence employees' physical and mental health within the workplace. It denotes a positive organizational climate that fosters quality of life at work and arises when individuals experience satisfaction in both professional and personal domains, leading to enhanced performance and productivity.

This article presents a theoretical review of the concept, aiming to explain its origins, main definitions, and the relevance of its implementation in companies. It also analyzes empirical studies conducted by various researchers who examined the relationship between organizational well-being and other workplace variables. The research followed a documentary and interpretative approach, based on an extensive review of literature drawn from recognized databases such as Scielo, Scopus, Google Scholar, Dialnet, and Redalyc.

The theoretical contribution of this work lies in the development of a conceptual framework that deepens the understanding of organizational well-being. Practically, it serves as a foundation for designing corporate strategies that enhance employee development and improve productivity.

The findings suggest that workplace well-being connects closely with variables such as organizational climate, culture, commitment, satisfaction, and stress. Consequently, healthy organizations are those that cultivate physical, psychological, and occupational well-being among their members, thereby reinforcing both individual fulfillment and collective performance.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Organizational Climate, Organizational Culture, Quality of Work Life.

Introduction

Organizational well-being (OW) has gained growing academic and managerial attention in recent years because of its influence on work performance, mental health, and talent retention within organizations. Also referred to as workplace well-being (WW), this construct has evolved from models centered on improving physical working conditions to frameworks that integrate psychological, emotional, and social dimensions.

OW has shifted from being perceived as a secondary concern to becoming a strategic priority for contemporary organizations. Empirical evidence demonstrates its direct impact on innovation, productivity, and organizational sustainability. Scholars such as Grajales (2023) propose viewing OW as a set of competencies that enable employees to make sound and autonomous decisions, thereby improving their quality of life and fulfilling personal and professional needs in dynamic environments.

Similarly, Cáceres-Lozano et al. (2023) conceptualize OW as an ongoing process that seeks to enhance and sustain appropriate working conditions, aiming to create healthy and harmonious environments that consider the interconnection between employees, families, and society. Calderón (2016) relates workplace well-being to mental health, positive relationships, life purpose, and autonomy, emphasizing that it reflects the emotional balance and physical health emerging from job satisfaction.

Castañeda et al. (2017) argue that employee well-being derives from safe and healthy work environments that foster mental stability, quality of life, and productivity. The authors emphasize the need for individuals to experience well-being, which arises when organizations prevent conditions that hinder task accomplishment and foster positive attitudes. Such an environment reduces obstacles and encourages enthusiasm, gratitude, and satisfaction among employees.

Hence, organizational well-being results from corporate strategies and actions shaped by psychological factors and by the extent to which employees engage in organizational processes that foster satisfaction within the workforce. Scholars have examined this construct from a psychological perspective—addressing motivation, perception, and emotion—and from a managerial viewpoint that encompasses organizational climate and culture (Bedoya et al., 2016).

When discussing workplace well-being, Blanco and Moros (2020) assert that healthy organizations develop and sustain employees' mental, social, and physical well-being through effective work processes, methods, and environments, which in turn lead to high levels of efficiency and productivity. The authors maintain that employee well-being directly correlates with organizational health. Such organizations rely on the dynamic interaction among health, performance, and workplace well-being; therefore, strengthening this connection becomes essential to enhance performance through well-defined and purpose-driven tasks (Angulo et al., 2021).

The purpose of this study involves describing the origins, conceptual foundations, and significance of organizational well-being for companies, as well as analyzing empirical research that has demonstrated its relationship with other organizational variables. In line with this objective, the following research questions guided the study: What are the origins and conceptual

definitions of organizational well-being? Which components constitute it? Why does it hold importance for organizations, and how does it relate to other variables in empirical studies?

Theoretically, this study develops a conceptual framework that deepens the understanding of organizational well-being by emphasizing its origins, clarifying key definitions, and examining the social, psychological, physical, cultural, and organizational factors that compose it and connect it to corporate productivity. From a practical standpoint, the research supports the design of business strategies aimed at enhancing employees' quality of life and strengthening organizational productivity.

To achieve the stated objective, an extensive literature review drew upon recognized databases such as Scielo, Scopus, Google Scholar, Dialnet, and Redalyc. The inclusion criteria encompassed peer-reviewed and indexed articles published between 2015 and 2025 in English and Spanish, classical books of relevance to management studies, peer-reviewed proceedings from international conferences, and doctoral dissertations from the last decade. The exclusion criteria eliminated undergraduate and master's theses, blogs, non-refereed articles, and both indexed and peer-reviewed publications older than ten years, as well as any material not appearing in scientific journals.

Methodological Limitations

Because this study follows a theoretical approach, it presents certain limitations inherent to this type of research. The literature review focused on articles written in English and Spanish, which may have excluded relevant information published in other languages. The search covered studies released between 2015 and 2025; therefore, earlier contributions that might have enriched the analysis remained outside the scope of review. Finally, the interpretation of the consulted bibliography relied on the author's own judgment, which could introduce a theoretical bias in the presentation of findings.

Background and Conceptual Framework of Organizational Well-Being

Organizational well-being traces its origins to the studies on organizations developed within the Human Relations School, particularly through Elton Mayo's experiments conducted between 1927 and 1932 at the Hawthorne plant of the Western Electric Company. Prior to this research, the National Research Council of the United States had carried out a study aimed at identifying the effects of lighting and other physical conditions on employee productivity (Koontz & Wehrich, 2004).

The findings revealed that changes in lighting, rest periods, working hours, and incentive pay failed to explain variations in productivity. Mayo and his collaborators concluded that productivity increases stemmed from social factors such as employee morale, satisfactory relationships among members of a work group, and management's ability to understand both individual and group behavior—guiding it through motivation, communication, counseling, and effective leadership (Koontz & Wehrich, 2004).

Castro (2018) explains that the notion of well-being originated in psychology and relates to the feeling of belonging and comfort within a community. This form of well-being expands from

the personal sphere to the broader social context and derives from the fulfillment of essential needs such as education, health, family relationships, work, income, and personal satisfaction. When these factors are adequately met, individuals experience well-being. From this psychological perspective, organizations seek to create work environments that strengthen both individual and collective dimensions of authenticity to achieve genuine well-being.

The term psychological well-being has often appeared in the literature as a synonym for happiness (Chumaceiro et al., 2023; Colín, 2017). However, Martins et al. (2023) differentiate between these concepts, arguing that happiness refers to the predominance of pleasure over negative emotions, whereas well-being represents a broader construct that encompasses both pleasure and personal growth.

Therefore, organizational well-being encompasses psychological dimensions that extend from the individual to the social level. It involves a sense of personal and collective fulfillment and depends on factors such as education, health, work, family, personal satisfaction, and income.

The concept transcends economic aspects because it integrates multiple human dimensions—family, occupational, cultural, and spiritual—that, although not directly related to employees' knowledge and skills, indirectly influence individual performance and, consequently, organizational outcomes (Arrieta et al., 2019).

Similarly, Patlán (2016) defines workplace well-being as a positive emotional state experienced by employees within their work environment, reflected in their level of vitality and the satisfaction derived from performing their tasks.

In this regard, workplace well-being involves the evaluations and emotions employees experience according to their level of satisfaction within the work environment. It aligns with other factors that foster positive states not only for the individual but also for their family, community, and the organization they belong to (Espinoza-Romo et al., 2021).

Workplace well-being represents a key construct in the study of organizational behavior, as it forms part of the sociocultural factors shaping organizational dynamics. Consequently, it becomes essential for managing work teams and business structures. Scholars have examined it from multiple perspectives—such as job satisfaction, psychological capital, commitment, and motivation—which collectively reflect how individuals function in their professional environment and how they perceive their quality of work life (Jiménez et al., 2020).

From a broader perspective, Shertzer et al. (2022) argue that the concept of organizational well-being integrates three essential dimensions. The first involves activities that promote pleasure and enjoyment for employees in the workplace through diverse practices such as teamwork initiatives, recreational days, and similar events that stimulate work motivation. The second dimension concerns the employee experience, which focuses on creating positive and engaging experiences throughout every stage of the employment cycle—from recruitment to performance evaluation. Finally, the third dimension relates to non-monetary benefits that, while not part of the employee's salary, enhance motivation, including sports programs, leisure activities, and product discounts.

Scholars such as Danna and Griffin (1999, cited in Arrieta et al., 2019) note that workplace well-being derives from multiple causes that, in turn, generate specific outcomes, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Diagram of Workplace Well-Being

Source: Arrieta et al. (2019, p. 75), adapted from Danna and Griffin (1999).

Figure 1 illustrates the model of workplace well-being, influenced by three key factors: the work environment, personal traits, and occupational stress. Within the work environment, several risks may arise—health hazards, safety threats, and other workplace dangers—that generate unsafe conditions negatively affecting employees’ health.

Personal traits encompass physiological, behavioral, cognitive, and emotional characteristics that emerge in challenging situations, often referred to as Type A tendencies. Personality attributes also include the belief in one’s ability to control events (locus of control). These personal traits play a crucial role in shaping well-being and occupational health within the organization.

Occupational stress involves work-related aspects such as job roles, organizational position, interpersonal relationships, organizational climate, and the interaction between family and work environments (Arrieta et al., 2019).

The Importance of Organizational Well-Being

Suárez (2024) emphasizes the relevance of employee well-being for organizations seeking to achieve their goals, outlining the following key propositions:

- Employee well-being directly influences productivity and performance. Therefore, organizations should implement programs that reduce stress and enhance workers' health, which in turn fosters commitment, efficiency, and a positive work environment.
- A workplace that nurtures well-being strengthens resilience. It enables employees to face challenges effectively and stimulates innovation within competitive contexts.
- Aligning work and personal life while providing adequate medical care reduces staff turnover. Such alignment increases loyalty and extends employees' tenure within the organization.
- Promoting a culture of well-being cultivates cohesive work teams. It encourages cooperation, minimizes conflict, and contributes to healthier work environments—factors that ultimately facilitate the attainment of organizational objectives.

The significance of workplace well-being lies in its recognition as a process that seeks to optimize employees' conditions within organizations, fostering their comprehensive development across both internal and external dimensions. Internally, it enhances job satisfaction, reinforces organizational identity, and strengthens the sense of belonging to the company. Externally, it promotes a reciprocal relationship between the employee, the workplace, and the family environment, thereby contributing to both organizational and social development through increased efficiency and performance.

Hence, workplace well-being acquires relevance for both employees and organizations as it enables individuals to achieve balance across physical, emotional, mental, and spiritual domains, leading to personal and familial satisfaction. In this context, workplace well-being emerges as a key element not only for employees but also for the organization as a whole (Arrieta et al., 2019).

Several scholars have underscored the importance of workplace well-being by examining its relationship with other organizational variables such as organizational climate and job commitment (García-Moncada et al., 2023; Gómez et al., 2019; Viitala et al., 2015); empowerment (Blanco & Moros, 2020); organizational culture (Joshi & Jaffer, 2024; Alarcón & Cubas, 2019; Chaparro, 2017); employee retention (Sameh et al., 2025); job and life satisfaction (Weziak-Bialowolska et al., 2020); and organizational stress (Martínez et al., 2022; Martínez-Mejía, 2022), among others. These studies demonstrate a close relationship between workplace well-being and these variables.

Table 1. Organizational Well-Being

Dimension	Description
Origin	– <i>Psychological</i> : a sense of personal and social well-being.— <i>Social</i> : morale, satisfactory relationships, motivation, communication, and leadership.— <i>Cultural</i> .
Concepts	– Activities designed to improve working conditions and create healthy environments.— Emotional state at work reflected through job satisfaction.—

Dimension	Description
	Individual and social psychological aspects depending on factors such as education, health, work, family, personal satisfaction, and income.
Importance	– <i>Internal</i> : promotes job satisfaction, identity, and sense of belonging; stimulates higher employee performance.– <i>External</i> : fosters relationships among the employee, the work environment, and the family context.
Approaches	– Models associated with psychological, emotional, and social variables.– Organizational structures encompassing job satisfaction, psychological capital, commitment, and motivation.
Outcomes	Positive mental health, life purpose, autonomy, satisfaction, job stability, quality of life, and productivity.

Empirical Studies on Organizational Well-Being

Among the studies that have demonstrated the relationship between organizational well-being and other variables, Gómez et al. (2019) conducted an analysis in a parcel delivery company aimed at statistically testing the correlation among organizational climate, workplace well-being, and organizational commitment. The research followed a quantitative, correlational, and cross-sectional design. The results showed that the dimensions of organizational climate and job commitment correlated significantly with workplace well-being. The authors concluded that both well-being and commitment levels increase when a positive organizational climate prevails.

An illustrative study by Weziak-Bialowolska et al. (2020) focused on a Mexican garment factory belonging to a global brand. The researchers sought to deepen the understanding of how well-being factors interact across life and work domains. A total of 954 employees participated by completing the Worker Well-Being Survey in a quantitative, longitudinal design. Data were collected on life satisfaction, job satisfaction, happiness, health, and social relationships. The findings revealed significant links between life satisfaction and job satisfaction, happiness and job satisfaction, and between life well-being and work well-being in relation to depression and meaning in life. The study also identified effects of workplace well-being on life well-being through social relationships. The authors emphasized that such studies are essential for understanding the life-work well-being ecosystem and for developing effective organizational interventions.

Joshi and Jaffer (2024) examined the influence of organizational culture on job stress and faculty well-being in higher education institutions, aiming to provide useful insights for creating a favorable environment for teachers that would ultimately enhance the quality of education and research. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were collected through surveys and interviews with professors from several institutions. The questionnaire achieved high reliability, verified through Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, ensuring validity of results. A confirmatory factor analysis yielded acceptable fit indices, indicating that the proposed model accurately represented the data structure. The findings highlighted that cultural factors such as positive leadership, effective communication, and sound labor policies strongly influence faculty well-being. Additionally, greater decision-making autonomy, collaboration, professional development, safe physical spaces, and job stability positively affected professors' well-being.

Another notable contribution came from Shertzer et al. (2022), who tested the hypothesis of a correlation between organizational well-being activities and job satisfaction in high-tech companies in Israel. Using a convenience sampling method, they surveyed male and female employees through two questionnaires—one on organizational well-being activities and another on job satisfaction—distributed via a social network of human resources managers from these firms. The results confirmed the proposed hypothesis, showing significant correlations among questionnaire items.

Collectively, these empirical studies demonstrate that employee well-being correlates positively with organizational climate, culture, and commitment; life and job satisfaction; social relationships; effective policies; leadership quality; workplace conditions; and professional development, among other variables. The evidence suggests that organizational well-being involves a set of deliberate activities that companies must implement to foster productivity, efficiency, and quality.

Conclusions

In contemporary organizational contexts, well-being functions as a crucial determinant of productivity. Empirical research has established its relationship with employee health, work efficiency, job stability, harmonious environments, autonomy, job and personal satisfaction, innovation, sustainability, income, education, and family balance.

Consequently, organizations must design and implement strategies that promote employee well-being through active participation in organizational processes, thereby enhancing job satisfaction. This approach requires integrating both organizational culture and climate as fundamental elements.

Institutions that prioritize employee well-being have been described as healthy organizations, characterized by efficient employees who maintain both physical and mental health as a result of positive work environments and well-defined, transparent processes.

The relevance of workplace well-being also lies in its close association with productivity and its capacity to foster resilient attitudes in the face of environmental challenges. Such attitudes reinforce identity, promote collaboration, and strengthen teamwork as a response to improved working conditions.

Finally, leaders, managers, and decision-makers who aim to ensure organizational growth, market permanence, and long-term success must incorporate employee well-being as a strategic pillar within their management agenda.

Future Research Directions

At the conclusion of this study, several opportunities for future research emerge. It would be valuable to incorporate both past and current studies conducted across diverse organizational and cultural contexts to deepen the understanding of organizational well-being. Future investigations should include practical studies that apply the concepts discussed in this paper

through quantitative and qualitative methodologies to provide empirical evidence. Finally, developing integrative models that combine the dimensions of organizational well-being would represent an important step toward fostering its implementation and promoting its application in organizational improvement initiatives.

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